

NOTES

Co-ordination Compounds of Indium

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The complex chemistry of indium is not very well-known although a number of anionic, neutral and cationic compounds are reported in the literature¹⁻⁵. The present note reports the isolation of a new series of compounds with picolinic and nicotinic acids as ligands. The empirical composition of these are found to be $[\text{In}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cl}]$ where ' $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N}$ ' is a picolinate or nicotinate radical. They are white crystalline solids practically insoluble in water and in common organic solvents. It appears that the chlorine atom is not ionic, but Ag^+ can precipitate all the Cl^- in dilute nitric acid solution in which the compounds are soluble. The presence of water molecule is indirectly established by the thermogravimetric studies. This is quite tightly bound to the metal atom and is only released by heating the compounds to a temperature of about 250° . The loss in weight at that temperature corresponds to the elimination of one molecule of water per molecule of the complex. The residue, on analysis, corresponds to the composition $[\text{In}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{O}_2\text{N})_2\text{Cl}]$ which may contain chlorine bridges. These dehydrated products start decomposition around 470° and the weight of the final residue corresponds to In_2O_3 .

Indium was determined by heating the compounds with concentrated sulphuric acid in tared platinum crucible and finally weighing after ignition as In_2O_3 . Chlorine was estimated as AgCl after decomposing the complex by peroxide fusion. Nitrogen was determined by micro Duma's method. The thermogravimetric analysis was done with a manual thermobalance.

Three equivalents, based on the indium taken, of picolinic or nicotinic acid was dissolved in a small quantity of dilute hydrochloric acid and was added to aqueous indium chloride solution. Strong ammonium hydroxide solution was then added dropwise with constant stirring, till the pH of the solution was 4.0-4.5 (for nicotinic acid) and 2.5-3.0 (for picolinic acid). The mixture was then boiled with stirring for a few minutes when the products were obtained as white crystalline

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precipitate. These were filtered, washed thoroughly with cold water, and finally with a little ethanol and dried at 105°. The dried products were analysed which gave :

For picolinate : In 28.1, N 6.65, Cl 8.54% ; loss in weight between 260°-300° (T. G. A.) 4.68% and at 260° (fixed) 4.37% ; Cl of the residue after heating to constant weight at 260°, 9.06%.

For nicotinate : In 27.7, N 6.54, Cl 8.57% ; loss in weight between 253°-300° (T. G. A.) 4.35% and at 260° (fixed) 4.49% ; Cl of the residue 9.1%. Calculated for [In(C₆H₄O₂N)₂(H₂O)Cl] : In 27.9, N 6.79, Cl 8.60, H₂O 4.36% and [In (C₆H₄O₂N)₂Cl] contains 9.0% chlorine.

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